

**Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 3**

Report on the online version of the data sets

Deliverable D3.3

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

Funded by the European Union. This work has received funding from the European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No 101093054.

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D3.3

About this document

Work package in charge: WP3 - Tackling the data challenge

Actual delivery date for this deliverable: 20.12.2024

Dissemination level: PU (for public use)

Lead author(s):

European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF): Sara Faghieh-Naini
Helsingin Yliopisto (UH): Juniper Tyree

Other contributing author(s):

Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC): Xavier Yepes-Arbós
Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum GmbH (DKRZ): Karsten Peters-von Gehlen
European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF): Peter Dueben
Helsingin Yliopisto (UH): Heikki Johannes Järvinen

Date	Submitted by	Reviewed by	Version (notes)
14.12.2024	Juniper Tyree	Jarmo Mäkelä	

Contact details

Project Office: esiwace3@bsc.es

Website: www.esiwace.eu

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/esiwace>

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/@esiwace880>

ESiWACE is on Zenodo, the Open Access repository for scientific results
<https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace>

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D3.3

Disclaimer: Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (JU). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of contents

1. Abstract / publishable summary	5
2. Conclusion & Results	5
3. Project objectives	5
4. Detailed report on the deliverable	6
4.1. Motivation for an Online Compression Laboratory	6
4.2. Overview of the Compression Laboratory Jupyter notebooks	7
4.3. Example datasets	10
4.3.1. IFS: atmospheric and wave model data from the hplp experiment	10
4.3.2. OpenIFS: HighResMIP based configuration	16
4.3.3. ICON: Global storm-resolving setup (NextGEMS)	21
4.3.4. ICON: Global climate projection setup (ICON-XPP)	23
4.4. Infrastructure of the Online Laboratory for Climate Science and Meteorology	26
4.5. Community outreach, and the Online Laboratory as a service	27
5. References	29
6. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered	31
7. How this deliverable contributes to the EuroHPC strategy	32
8. Sustainability	32
9. Community engagement, dissemination, and exploitation	32
9.1 Target audience	32
9.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable	33
9.3 Publications in preparation OR submitted	33
9.4 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable	33

1. Abstract / publishable summary

This deliverable documents the development of an Online Laboratory for Data Compression in Climate Science and Meteorology and the publication of the data compression datasets that allow the testing of various compression methods for output of both weather and climate models.

The Jupyter notebooks of the compression laboratory can be used to explore several datasets for medium-range weather predictions and climate simulations, apply lossless and lossy compression techniques in an easy-to-use way, and allow to perform a number of diagnostics to evaluate possible degradations of data's information content due to lossy compression. We also provide an online laboratory as a service, which hosts the compression laboratory notebooks and allows users to quickly jump in and explore compression without needing to install or set up anything.

The provided weather prediction and climate simulation datasets, produced from the IFS model, the OpenIFS model and the ICON model, can be accessed and explored within the online laboratory or downloaded directly from an S3 bucket.

Based on the developments of this deliverable D3.3 and milestone M3.3, the team working on the compression task will organise community outreach, including a hackathon, to explore compression techniques in detail over the next two years. We will also explore and document potential trade-offs between a reduction of the data that need to be stored, the computational cost to compress and decompress the data, and the compression error that will impact diagnostics performed on top of the stored data.

2. Conclusion & Results

Four simulation datasets of three models for the atmosphere (D3.3) have been established and are now available for download from S3 buckets. The compression laboratory (M3.3) has been developed and allows easy access to the data, easy application of a number of lossless and lossy compression techniques, and the application and visualisation of various diagnostics by domain scientists and users. We are now ready to perform a more detailed evaluation of lossy compression for weather and climate data in the next two years, and to use the published datasets and compression laboratory as the basis of our community outreach including a hackathon.

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to achieving all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Grant Agreement:

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
A1: Transfer and establish knowledge and technology for efficient and scalable simulations of weather and climate across the Earth system modelling community in Europe.	Yes

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D3.3

A2: Close common technology gaps in the knowledge and toolbox for high-resolution Earth system modelling via joint developments across the European community.	Yes
A3: Serve as a sustainable community hub for training, communication, and dissemination for high-performance computing for weather and climate modelling in Europe.	Yes

Specific goals in the work plan	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1: Increase efficiency of weather and climate simulations on state-of-the-art supercomputers.	No
O2: Design tools to close technology gaps for high performance computing.	No
O3: Develop tools to tackle the data challenge of high-resolution weather and climate modelling.	Yes
O4: Support the wider community of weather and climate modelling in the use of state-of-the-art supercomputers via targeted services.	No
O5: Support the wider community of weather and climate modelling in the use of state-of-the-art supercomputers via training and capacity building.	No
O6: Build a well-connected and inclusive community for high-resolution Earth system modelling across Earth system science and HPC and establish connections and knowledge transfer between existing European initiatives.	No

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

This section provides an overview of why we have developed a compression laboratory (4.1.), the Jupyter notebooks (4.2.), and the datasets (4.3.) published with it. It also introduces the Online Laboratory for Climate Science and Meteorology service that hosts the compression laboratory (4.4.), and outlines our plans for using the online compression laboratory in community outreach for research on safe lossy data compression for weather and climate science.

4.1. Motivation for an Online Compression Laboratory

The output volumes from high-resolution weather and climate models are increasing exponentially and have long reached the exascale (10^{18} bytes) for data storage [6]. Higher-resolution models with larger ensembles and more complex processes are an essential part of the EU's fight against the climate crisis via the prediction and preparation for its effects. Data compression is required to tackle this data challenge so that the data volumes do not impede the technical and scientific progress in weather and climate modelling and the gain in knowledge production resulting from it. While numerous advances in the field of lossy data compression have been made that promise compression factors of $O(10)$ (e.g. ZFP [2, 19], Bit Information [17], or SZ3 [18, 36]) and $O(100)$ - $O(1000)$ (e.g. using implicit neural networks [15]), they have generally not been taken up by the research and operational weather and climate prediction communities. Domain scientists instead hold reservations that lossy compression may result in the loss of problem-specific information and thus impact the analyses they perform. There is also concern about the reproducibility of lossy compression when publishing open-access datasets. In ESiWACE3 T3.3, we are working to bridge this gap by determining the requirements that domain

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D3.3

scientists have for compression-induced errors for different fields (e.g. temperature vs specific humidity vs wind speed) and identifying which compression methods can satisfy these requirements. In effect, we want to make it easy and fearless for domain scientists to apply lossy compression to deal with their ever-increasing data volumes.

Determining the weather and climate community's requirements and alleviating their fears about lossy compression both require community outreach, contributions, and feedback. We aim to make it as easy as possible to try out different compression methods on various data, including the researcher's own model run outputs, so that experimenting with compression can fit into the time of a coffee break and alleviating fears and sharing their domain-specific requirements is not hindered by any time-consuming setup.

We have thus developed an Online Laboratory for Climate Science and Meteorology (<https://lab.climet.eu>), and several Jupyter [14] notebooks that explore data compression and can be quickly run in the Online Laboratory. We refer to this combination as the Online Compression Laboratory. While the notebooks can also be run outside the Online Laboratory (e.g. in a local Python environment or on high performance computers), running them inside is as simple as opening a website (<https://compression.lab.climet.eu>), alleviates the time of setting up a fresh Python environment, and allows experimentation with compression to begin in under one minute. The Online Laboratory is not restricted to data compression, but has instead been designed to be useful to the broader community as a JupyterLab-like service that allows easy sharing of executable Jupyter notebooks that run within a Python environment that is already set up and configured for the weather and climate community. We envision that the Online Laboratory may be used to provide interactive documentation examples for community software and to publish zero-setup reproducible experiments alongside scientific publications and presentations. Due to its ease of use, we hope that it also invites new users outside our community, e.g. interested citizens, to engage with European weather and climate modelling.

The Online Laboratory for Climate Science and Meteorology and the notebooks exploring data compression have been developed by ESiWACE3 T3.3 starting in May 2023. The community-developed technology that the Online Laboratory builds on is discussed in more detail in section 4.4.

4.2. Overview of the Compression Laboratory Jupyter notebooks

The compression laboratory consists of several notebooks that introduce data compression and allow for an easy application and the analysis of several datasets. These notebooks are developed in the open-source CC-BY-4.0-licensed GitHub repository

<https://github.com/climet-eu/compression-lab-notebooks>

Version 0.2 of the notebooks has been published as part of this deliverable and can be accessed at <https://github.com/climet-eu/compression-lab-notebooks/releases/tag/v0.2> on GitHub, [doi:10.5281/zenodo.14526226](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14526226) on Zenodo, and <https://compression.lab.climet.eu/v0.2> in the online laboratory (see section 4.4).

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D3.3

Figure 1: Screenshot of the compression laboratory when it is launched inside the online laboratory.

This section provides a brief overview of the available notebooks:

- `01-intro.ipynb`: First introduction to the online laboratory, data loading, compression, and visualisation
- `02-data-sources/`: Small examples on how to open datasets from different sources
 - `01-local.ipynb`: open a large local read-only dataset by mounting it into the lab
 - `02-remote.ipynb`: open large remote datasets using `fsspec`, `kerchunk`, and `zarr`
 - `03-cdsapi.ipynb`: download small datasets from the Climate Data Store using the `cdsapi`
 - `04-ecmwfapi.ipynb`: download small datasets from the ECMWF Archive using the `ecmwfapi`
- `03-examples/`: Longer walkthrough examples that apply and evaluate data compression on different variables
 - `01-compressors.ipynb`: comparison of different compressors on a small temperature and specific humidity dataset
- `04-example-datasets/`: Example datasets and access via an S3 bucket
 - `01-hp1p.ipynb`: open `hp1p`-experiment dataset from the ECMWF S3 bucket
 - `02-OpenIFS.ipynb`: open `OpenIFS`-experiment dataset from the ECMWF S3 bucket
 - `03-NextGEMS.ipynb`: open `NextGEMS`-experiment dataset from the ECMWF S3 bucket
 - `04-ICONXPP.ipynb`: open `ICON-XPP`-experiment dataset from the ECMWF S3 bucket

Section 4.3. provides detail on the example datasets that have been published alongside the compression laboratory and the Jupyter notebooks (inside `04-example-datasets/`) that explore them.

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D3.3

The compression laboratory uses the `numcodecs` API [34] for compressing n-dimensional array data. In addition to the algorithms supported directly by `numcodecs`, the compression laboratory also provides further algorithms through the still-in-development `fcbench.codecs` package. Using `fcbench` and `numcodecs`, a compressor can be defined as a stack of codecs, e.g.

```
bitround_compressor = [  
    fcbench.codecs.BitRound(keepbits=6), # only keep 6 mantissa bits  
    fcbench.codecs.Zlib(level=9),      # lossless compression  
]
```

or

```
zfp_compressor = [  
    fcbench.codecs.Zfp(mode="fixed-accuracy", tolerance=1e-3),  
]
```

Analysing the effect of (lossy) compression is simplified via the `fcbench.compressor.compress_decompress(a, compressor)` helper function which compresses and decompresses an array (`numpy.array` or `xarray.DataArray`) and returns the decompressed array. It also produces some statistics that inform about the compression ratio of each codec in the compressor stack (how much it compresses), and how much time it took to compress/decompress the data (the wall-time). For codecs provided by the `fcbench.codecs` package, the statistics also include a cross-platform reproducible instruction count measurement for each codec that provides a non-noisy alternative to wall-time for measuring how fast the compressor is. These statistics help evaluate the trade-off between higher compression ratios and higher computational cost.

The compression lab notebooks also show how datasets can be easily visualised using the `earthkit.plots` package that is being developed by ECMWF (independent of ESIWACE3). A common workflow in the examples is to first plot the original data, then the compressed data, and finally the compression error to provide quick visual feedback on the quality of compression.

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D3.3

Figure 2: Screenshot of a compression error plot for a compressor with high information loss.

The `03-examples/01-compressors.ipynb` provides an example comparison of different compression algorithms using the above visual and performance measuring methods. It also shows how the compression errors can be analysed to provide a summary table that provides a quantitative evaluation of the different methods. It is important to note that this notebook currently only showcases how such a comparison workflow can look like but does not yet provide a comprehensive comparison of compression methods. We are actively working on case studies that will examine one or more variables in detail and explore how current compression methods can be safely applied to them. We plan that a collection of such case studies and adjacent research within the next two years will result in one or more summary notebooks that provide concrete recommendations for data compression.

4.3. Example datasets

The following subsections provide an overview of the available datasets, along with guidance on how to access and work with them. Four different distinct datasets, with a total volume of approximately 600 GB, are publicly accessible via the [ECMWF S3 bucket](#) [9].

The datasets comprise an IFS and an OpenIFS weather forecast and two ICON climate simulations. These datasets will serve as the foundation for the data compression hackathon, taking place in the second half of ESiWACE3. During the event, various compression techniques will be closely analyzed, e.g. using these datasets. Detailed insights into each dataset are presented in this and the following subsections.

4.3.1. IFS: atmospheric and wave model data from the hplp experiment

The first dataset contains uncompressed IEEE-754 Standard (1985) 64-bit floating-point outputs from the atmospheric and wave model (long window 4Dvar) for experiment version [hplp](#) [8]. This dataset was specifically selected as it represents a medium-range IFS weather forecast and is stored in a 64-bit floating-point format without compression.

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D3.3

The simulation was conducted on a reduced Gaussian octahedral grid (Tco399), corresponding to a horizontal resolution of approximately 28 km, and with 137 vertical model levels. The 10-day weather forecast is provided in 12-hour intervals, beginning from 2020-07-21 at 00:00:00 UTC.

Surface, model and pressure level data are available for the atmospheric model. A detailed overview of the parameters, i.e., model output variables, is provided in the tables below. Some parameters are defined on the 0400 reduced Gaussian grid (*reduced_gg*), others as spherical harmonic coefficients (*sh*), and wave model parameters are specified on the reduced lat-lon grid (*reduced_ll*).

Only the short names of the parameters are listed here. More information on them including full names, units and detailed explanations can be found in the [ECMWF Parameter database](#) [7].

Model level parameters:

<i>paramId</i>	<i>shortName</i>	<i>gridName</i>	<i>gridType</i>	<i>typeOfLevel</i>	<i>packingType</i>
75	crwc	0400	reduced_gg	hybrid	grid_ieee
76	cswc	0400	reduced_gg	hybrid	grid_ieee
129	z	-	sh	hybrid	grid_ieee
130	t	-	sh	hybrid	grid_ieee
133	q	0400	reduced_gg	hybrid	grid_ieee
135	w	-	sh	hybrid	grid_ieee
138	vo	-	sh	hybrid	grid_ieee
152	lnsp	-	sh	hybrid	grid_ieee
155	d	-	sh	hybrid	spectral_ieee
131	u	-	sh	hybrid	spectral_ieee
132	v	-	sh	sh	spectral_ieee
203	o3	0400	reduced_gg	sh	spectral_ieee
246	clwc	0400	reduced_gg	sh	spectral_ieee
247	ciwc	0400	reduced_gg	sh	spectral_ieee
248	cc	0400	reduced_gg	sh	spectral_ieee

Table 1: Model level variable specification for the supplied IFS simulation; Spatial resolution: 28 km, temporal output frequency: 12-hourly; GRIB data in the S3 bucket: "hplp/hplp_ml_"

Pressure level parameters:

<i>paramId</i>	<i>shortName</i>	<i>gridName</i>	<i>gridType</i>	<i>typeOfLevel</i>	<i>packingType</i>
129	z	-	sh	isobaricInhPa	spectral_complex
130	t	-	sh	isobaricInhPa	spectral_complex
133	q	0400	reduced_gg	isobaricInhPa	spectral_complex
135	w	-	sh	isobaricInhPa	spectral_complex
138	vo	-	sh	isobaricInhPa	spectral_complex
155	d	-	sh	isobaricInhPa	spectral_complex
131	u	-	sh	isobaricInhPa	spectral_complex
132	v	-	sh	isobaricInhPa	spectral_complex
157	r	-	sh	isobaricInhPa	spectral_complex

Table 2: Pressure level variable specification for the supplied IFS simulation; Spatial resolution: 28 km, temporal output frequency: 12-hourly; GRIB data in the S3 bucket: "hplp/hplp_pl_"

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D3.3

All surface-level parameters are stored on a *reduced_gg* grid at the surface level, using the packing type *grid_ieee*. The following *paramIds* and their corresponding *shortNames* are available:

Surface level parameters:

<i>paramId</i>	<i>shortName</i>	<i>paramId</i>	<i>shortName</i>	<i>paramId</i>	<i>shortName</i>
8	sro	147	slhf	209	ttrc
9	ssro	148	chnk	210	ssrc
31	ci	151	msl	211	strc
32	asn	159	blh	212	tisr
33	rsn	164	tcc	213	vimd
34	sst	165	10u	228	tp
35	istl1	166	10v	229	iews
36	istl2	167	2t	230	inss
37	istl3	168	2d	231	ishf
38	istl4	169	ssrd	232	ie
39	swvl1	170	stl2	235	skt
40	swvl2	172	lsm	236	stl4
41	swvl3	175	strd	238	tsn
42	swvl4	176	ssr	243	fal
44	es	177	str	244	fsr
45	smlt	178	tsr	245	flsr
47	dsrp	179	ttr	3020	vis
49	10fg	180	ewss	151131	ocu
50	lspf	181	nsss	151132	ocv
57	uvb	182	e	228001	cin
58	par	183	stl3	228029	i10fg
59	cape	186	lcc	228089	tcrw
78	tclw	187	mcc	228090	tcsw
79	tciw	188	hcc	228216	fzra
129	z	189	sund	228217	ilspf
136	tcw	195	lgws	228218	crr
137	tcwv	196	mgws	228219	lsrr
139	stl1	197	gwd	228220	csfr
141	sd	198	src	228221	lssfr
142	lsp	201	mx2t	228251	pev
143	cp	202	mn2t	260015	ptype
144	sf	205	ro	260121	kx
145	bld	206	tco3	260123	totalx
146	sshf	208	tsrc		

Table 3: Surface level variable specification for the supplied IFS simulation; Spatial resolution: 28 km, temporal output frequency: 12-hourly; GRIB data in the S3 bucket: "hplp/hplp_sfc.grib"

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D3.3

Wave model parameters:

<i>paramId</i>	<i>shortName</i>	<i>gridName</i>	<i>gridType</i>	<i>typeOfLevel</i>	<i>packingType</i>
140208	wstar	-	reduced_ll	meanSea	grid_simple
140209	rhoao	-	reduced_ll	meanSea	grid_simple
140212	phioc	-	reduced_ll	meanSea	grid_simple
140214	tauoc	-	reduced_ll	meanSea	grid_simple
140215	ust	-	reduced_ll	meanSea	grid_simple
140216	vst	-	reduced_ll	meanSea	grid_simple
140218	hmax	-	reduced_ll	meanSea	grid_simple
140219	wmb	-	reduced_ll	meanSea	grid_simple
140220	mp1	-	reduced_ll	meanSea	grid_simple
140221	mp2	-	reduced_ll	meanSea	grid_simple
140222	wdw	-	reduced_ll	meanSea	grid_simple
140229	swh	-	reduced_ll	meanSea	grid_simple
140230	mwd	-	reduced_ll	meanSea	grid_simple
140231	pp1d	-	reduced_ll	meanSea	grid_simple
140232	mwp	-	reduced_ll	meanSea	grid_simple
140233	cdww	-	reduced_ll	heightAboveGround	grid_simple
140245	wind	-	reduced_ll	heightAboveGround	grid_simple
140249	dwi	-	reduced_ll	heightAboveGround	grid_simple

Table 4: Wave model variable specification for the supplied IFS simulation; Spatial resolution: 28 km, temporal output frequency: 12-hourly; GRIB data in the S3 bucket: "hplp/hplp_wave.grib"

These data are stored in the GRIB file format, which is the WMO's standard format for binary gridded data. For more detailed information, please refer to the [WMO guide](#) [33].

These data are publicly available in the [hplp directory](#) [11] of the ESiWACE S3 bucket. These data are published under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0). <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

The total size of the data is approximately 187 GB, and the following files are available:

Model level data on a reduced_gg grid (split into two files):

- `hplp_ml_reduced_gg_levels_0_120.grib`: steps 0-120 (2020-07-21T00:00:00 to 2020-07-26T00:00:00)
- `hplp_ml_reduced_gg_levels_132_240.grib`: steps 132-240 (2020-07-26T12:00:00 to 2020-07-31T00:00:00)

Model level data stored as spherical harmonic coefficients (sh):

- `hplp_ml_sh.grib`: original data (sh coefficients cannot be plotted directly)
- `hplp_ml_sh_0400.grib`: remapped onto an 0400 grid for visualization

Pressure level data on a reduced_gg grid:

- `hplp_pl_reduced_gg.grib`

Pressure level data stored as spherical harmonic coefficients (sh):

- `hplp_pl_sh.grib`: original data (sh coefficients cannot be plotted directly)
- `hplp_pl_sh_0400.grib`: remapped onto an 0400 grid for visualization

Surface level data on reduced_gg:

- `hplp_sfc.grib`

Wave model data on reduced_ll grid:

- `hplp_wave.grib`

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D3.3

To avoid downloading the entire dataset up-front, indexing metadata is stored alongside the files as `<grib_filename>.ref`. These index files, which follow the `fsspec` and `kerchunk` specification for reference file systems [3], were generated offline using the `gribscan` package and allow the GRIB files to be accessed using the `fsspec` and `zarr` packages, thus providing support for lazy, chunked, and asynchronous loading of GRIB data from any filesystem-like source (here an S3 bucket) without the GRIB driver `cf_grib` needing to support it directly. The actual data are only fetched when they are requested by the user, for example, by inspecting the data values or visualizing a variable. The preprocessing needs to be performed offline since generating the GRIB metadata requires scanning the entire GRIB file.

The data can be downloaded via the following link:

<https://object-store.os-api.cci1.ecmwf.int/esiwacebucket/hplp/<filename>>

A Jupyter notebook that explains the entire dataset, including a helper function to load the desired data into an `xarray`, is available here:

- <https://github.com/climet-eu/compression-lab-notebooks/blob/v0.2/04-example-datasets/01-hplp.ipynb> on GitHub
- <https://compression.lab.climet.eu/v0.2/04-example-datasets/01-hplp.ipynb> in the Online Compression Laboratory (see section 4.4)
- [doi:10.5281/zenodo.14526226](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14526226) on Zenodo

The following screenshots provide an overview of the dataset description, the helper function for loading the data, and an example of how to plot them.

IFS hplp experiment data

This notebook is a comprehensive guide to accessing GRIB files for the `hplp` experiment. It includes details about the available parameters, levels, and steps, along with instructions for using the `load_hplp_data` function to access these files from the `ECMWF S3 bucket`. The GRIB files are not downloaded locally; instead, they are accessed remotely using `gribscan`, `fsspec`, and `zarr` via their corresponding `.ref` metadata files (also hosted in the S3 bucket), which were produced up-front using `gribscan`.

Experiment Details and Available Data Fields

The dataset contains uncompressed IEEE-754 Standard (1985) 64-bit floating-point single-time atmospheric and wave model (long window 4Dvar) outputs from the IFS. The simulation was conducted on a reduced Gaussian octahedral grid (Tco399), corresponding to a horizontal resolution of approximately 28 km, and with 137 vertical model levels. The 10-day weather forecast is provided in 12-hour intervals, beginning from 2020-07-21 at 00:00:00 UTC. The total volume of the available dataset is about 187 GB.

The GRIB files are organized into different types of data fields based on the levels at which they are stored. These data are published under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) license: <https://apps.ecmwf.int/datasets/licences/general/>.

Pressure Level Parameters

The following parameters are available as pressure level fields:

```
["z", "t", "q", "w", "vo", "d", "u", "v", "r"]
```

These parameters are stored at the following pressure levels (in hPa):

```
[1, 2, 3, 5, 7, 10, 20, 30, 50, 70, 100, 150, 200, 250, 300, 400, 500, 700, 850, 925, 1000]
```

The corresponding IDs and more information are given in the table below:

paramid	gridName	gridType	typeOfLevel	shortName	packingType
129	-	sh	isobaricInhPa	z	spectral_complex
130	-	sh	isobaricInhPa	t	spectral_complex
133	O400	reduced_gg	isobaricInhPa	q	spectral_complex
135	-	sh	isobaricInhPa	w	spectral_complex
138	-	sh	isobaricInhPa	vo	spectral_complex
155	-	sh	isobaricInhPa	d	spectral_complex
131	-	sh	isobaricInhPa	u	spectral_complex
132	-	sh	isobaricInhPa	v	spectral_complex
157	-	sh	isobaricInhPa	r	spectral_complex

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D3.3

Figure 3: Screenshot of the notebook about the hplp dataset: parameter description.

Figure 4: Screenshot of the notebook about the hplp dataset: load_hplp_data function.

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D3.3

Figure 6: Screenshot of the notebook about the hplp dataset: loading and plotting data.

4.3.2. OpenIFS: HighResMIP based configuration

The second dataset contains uncompressed IEEE-754 Standard (1985) 64-bit floating-point output from the OpenIFS 43r3 model. This dataset was selected for the reasons given in Sec. 6.

The simulation was conducted on a reduced Gaussian octahedral grid (Tco1279), corresponding to a horizontal resolution of approximately 9 km. The 5-day forecast was run with a time step length of 600 seconds (10 minutes) using a High Resolution Model Intercomparison Project (HighResMIP) based output configuration. The HighResMIP was a CMIP6 endorsed Model Intercomparison Project and applied, for the first time, a multi-model approach to the systematic investigation of the impact of horizontal resolution.

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D3.3

The available data include the following pressure level fields:

<i>parameter</i>	<i>long name</i>
q	specific humidity
r	relative humidity
t	temperature
u	U component of wind
v	V component of wind
vo	vorticity (relative)
w	vertical velocity(diagnostic)
z	geopotential

Table 5: Pressure level variable specification for the supplied OpenIFS simulation; Spatial resolution: 9 km, temporal output frequency: 6-hourly; NetCDF data in the S3 bucket: "OpenIFS/HighResMIP_6h_reduced_pl_<variable_name>.nc"

The available time steps for the pressure level data start at 2009-10-15 18:00:00 UTC, increasing in 6-hour steps to 2009-10-20 12:00:00 UTC.

Furthermore, the following surface fields are available:

<i>parameter</i>	<i>long name</i>
10u	10 metre U wind component
10v	10 metre V wind component
2d	2 metre dewpoint temperature
2t	2 metre temperature
cp	convective precipitation
e	evaporation
es	snow evaporation
ewss	time-integrated eastward turbulent surface stress
msl	mean sea level pressure
nsss	time-integrated northward turbulent surface stress
ro	water runoff and drainage
rsn	snow density
sd	snow depth
sf	snowfall
skt	skin temperature
slhf	time-integrated surface latent heat net flux
smlt	snowmelt
sp	surface pressure
sro	surface runoff
sshf	time-integrated surface sensible heat net flux
ssr	surface net short-wave (solar) radiation
ssrc	surface net short-wave (solar) radiation, clear sky
ssrd	surface short-wave (solar) radiation downwards
stl1	soil temperature level 1
stl2	soil temperature level 2

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D3.3

stl3	soil temperature level 3
stl4	soil temperature level 4
str	surface net long-wave (thermal) radiation
strc	surface net long-wave (thermal) radiation, clear sky
strd	surface long-wave (thermal) radiation downwards
swvl1	volumetric soil water layer 1
swvl2	volumetric soil water layer 2
swvl3	volumetric soil water layer 3
swvl4	volumetric soil water layer 4
tcc	Total Cloud Cover
tciw	total column cloud ice water
tclw	total column cloud liquid water
tcwv	total column vertically-integrated water vapour
tisr	TOA incident short-wave (solar) radiation
tp	Total Precipitation
tsn	temperature of snow layer
tsr	top net short-wave (solar) radiation
tsrc	top net short-wave (solar) radiation, clear sky
ttr	top net long-wave (thermal) radiation
ttrc	top net long-wave (thermal) radiation, clear sky

Table 6: Surface level variable specification for the supplied OpenIFS simulation; Spatial resolution: 9 km, temporal output frequency: 3-hourly; NetCDF data in the S3 bucket: "OpenIFS/HighResMIP_3h_reduced_sfc.nc"

The available time steps for the surface level data start at 2009-10-15 15:00:00 UTC, increasing in 3-hour steps to 2009-10-20 12:00:00 UTC.

More information on the parameters including full names, units and detailed explanations can again be found in the [ECMWF Parameter database](#) [7]. The data are stored in the [NetCDF file format](#) [31] and are publicly available in the [OpenIFS directory](#) [13] of the ESiWACE S3 bucket. These data are published under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC BY 4.0) <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

The total size of the data is approximately 258 GB, and the following files are available:

Pressure level data (one file for each parameter):

- HighResMIP_6h_reduced_pl_q.nc
- HighResMIP_6h_reduced_pl_r.nc
- HighResMIP_6h_reduced_pl_t.nc
- HighResMIP_6h_reduced_pl_u.nc
- HighResMIP_6h_reduced_pl_v.nc
- HighResMIP_6h_reduced_pl_vo.nc
- HighResMIP_6h_reduced_pl_w.nc
- HighResMIP_6h_reduced_pl_z.nc

Surface level data (single file):

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D3.3

- HighResMIP_3h_reduced_sfc.nc

Also here, to avoid downloading the entire dataset up-front, indexing metadata is stored alongside the files as `<netcdf_filename>.ref`. These index files, which follow the `fsspec` and `kerchunk` specification for reference file systems [3], were generated offline using the `kerchunk` library and allow the NetCDF files to be accessed using the `fsspec` and `zarr` packages, thus providing support for lazy, chunked, and asynchronous loading of NetCDF data from any filesystem-like source (here an S3 bucket) without the NetCDF driver (e.g. `netCDF4` or `h5netcdf`) needing to support it directly. The actual data are again only fetched when they are requested by the user, for example, by inspecting the data values or visualizing a variable. While we have extracted the metadata offline for ease of use, it can also be extracted at runtime since NetCDF files have separate metadata. This online extraction is demonstrated in the following Jupyter notebook:

- <https://github.com/climet-eu/compression-lab-notebooks/blob/v0.2/02-data-sources/02-remote.ipynb> on GitHub
- <https://compression.lab.climet.eu/v0.2/02-data-sources/02-remote.ipynb> in the Online Compression Laboratory (see section 4.4)
- [doi:10.5281/zenodo.14526226](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14526226) on Zenodo

The data can be downloaded via the following link:

<https://object-store.os-api.cci1.ecmwf.int/esiwacebucket/OpenIFS/<filename>>

A Jupyter notebook that explains the entire dataset, including a helper function to load the desired data into an `xarray`, is available here:

- <https://github.com/climet-eu/compression-lab-notebooks/blob/v0.2/04-example-datasets/02-OpenIFS.ipynb> on GitHub
- <https://compression.lab.climet.eu/v0.2/04-example-datasets/02-OpenIFS.ipynb> in the Online Compression Laboratory (see section 4.4)
- [doi:10.5281/zenodo.14526226](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14526226) on Zenodo

The notebook is structured similarly to the one explained in Sec. 4.3.1., so we only provide one screenshot explaining the helper function to load the data.

Figure 7: Screenshot of the notebook about the OpenIFS dataset: `load_OpenIFS_data` function.

4.3.3. ICON: Global storm-resolving setup (NextGEMS)

ICON data produced within the NextGEMS project [32] are supplied for testing and compression analysis purposes. These data were produced within the 4th model cycle phase of the NextGEMS project and are published under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license. The simulation of which data is provided, NGC4008, spans a total of 30 years, uses an ssp370-like scenario run from 2020 and is run at an R2B8/8 resolution, which corresponds to about 10km horizontal spacing for both atmospheric and oceanic grids. Higher resolution simulations have been performed, but not for such long time periods due to resource constraints.

For reasons of resource limitation, we only provide a small subset of data from this simulation in the S3 bucket; the full size of the simulation ngc4008 amounts to about 500TB. We therefore provide a 3-months (2 Jan 2020 - 31 March 2020) long dataset of 4 selected variables.

<i>parameter</i>	<i>variable name</i>	<i>levels</i>
precipitation	pr	near surface
v-wind	va	near surface, ~5km, ~10km
u-wind	ua	near surface, ~5km, ~10km
specific humidity	hus	near surface, ~5km, ~10km

Table 7: Variable specification for the supplied ICON ngc4008 simulations; Spatial resolution: 10km, temporal output frequency: daily; zarr-store in the S3 bucket: EW3_ICON_ngc4008_90d_Compression_test.zarr.

More information and useful hints on using this dataset are supplied in the NextGEMS-related online resource [5, 20].

The data are provided as a lossless compressed Zarr dataset and are stored on a HEALPix grid, of which we supply the highest spatial resolution available for this dataset (10km grid spacing, see above).

The data are stored in the [Zarr](#) [35] and are publicly available in a [Zarr directory](#) [12] of the ESiWACE S3 bucket. The total size of the data, contained in the EW3_ICON_ngc4008_90d_Compression_test.zarr directory, is approximately 9 GB. The data are available for reuse under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

Supplying the data in lossless-compressed Zarr format on HEALPix grid very closely mimics the currently adopted approach for high-resolution output from ICON simulations, in particular for the NextGEMS simulations. As the dataset has only been compressed using lossless methods, we can test lossy and lossless compression on this dataset as if it was not compressed at all.

The data can be downloaded via the following link:

https://object-store.os-api.cci1.ecmwf.int/esiwacebucket/EW3_ICON_ngc4008_90d_Compression_test.zarr/

A Jupyter notebook that explains the entire dataset, including a helper function to load the desired data into an `xarray`, is available here:

- <https://github.com/climet-eu/compression-lab-notebooks/blob/v0.2/04-example-datasets/03-NextGEMS.ipynb> on GitHub
- <https://compression.lab.climet.eu/v0.2/04-example-datasets/03-NextGEMS.ipynb> in the Online Compression Laboratory (see section 4.4)

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D3.3

- [doi:10.5281/zenodo.14526226](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14526226) on Zenodo

The notebook is structured similarly to the one explained in Sec. 4.3.1., so we only provide one screenshot explaining the helper function to load the data.

Using the `load_NextGEMS_data` Function

To load the Zarr directory, you can use the following function:

```
load_NextGEMS_data()
```

This function is straightforward and does not require any parameters.

```
[1]: # URL of S3 bucket
BASE_URL = "https://object-store.os-api.cc11.ecmwf.int/esiwacebucket"
```

First, the package `zarr` (modern dataset format that is specifically designed for chunked access) and its dependencies need to be imported for the remote access.

```
[2]: import aiohttp
import dask
import fsspec
import zarr
```

[pyodide]: Loading Jinja2, MarkupSafe, aiohappyeyeballs, aiohttp, aiosignal, asciitree, async-timeout, attrs, click, cloudpickle, dask, frozenli

The `load_NextGEMS_data` function simplifies remote access to Zarr datasets stored on the S3 bucket. It loads the data efficiently as an xarray dataset.

```
[3]: import json
import requests
import xarray as xr

def load_NextGEMS_data():
    url = f"{BASE_URL}/EW3_ICON_ngc4008_90d_Compression_test.zarr"

    print(f"Loading dataset {url}")

    return xr.open_dataset(url, engine="zarr", chunks=dict())
```

[pyodide]: Loading pandas, pyarrow, pyodide-unix-timezones, python-dateutil, pytz, tzdata, xarray...

Example Usage

To load the Zarr directory, you can use the following example. This will load the whole dataset.

```
[4]: ds = load_NextGEMS_data()
ds
```

Loading dataset https://object-store.os-api.cc11.ecmwf.int/esiwacebucket/EW3_ICON_ngc4008_90d_Compression_test.zarr

```
[4]: xarray.Dataset
```

► Dimensions: (time: 90, level_full: 3, cell: 3145728)

▼ Coordinates:

level_full	(level_full)	float64	89.0 65.0 55.0	📄 🗑
time	(time)	datetime64[ns]	2020-01-02 ... 2020-03-31	📄 🗑

▼ Data variables:

hus	(time, level_full, cell)	float32	dask.array<chunksize=(3, 1, 196608), meta...	📄 🗑
pr	(time, cell)	float32	dask.array<chunksize=(3, 196608), meta...	📄 🗑
ua	(time, level_full, cell)	float32	dask.array<chunksize=(3, 1, 196608), meta...	📄 🗑
va	(time, level_full, cell)	float32	dask.array<chunksize=(3, 1, 196608), meta...	📄 🗑

Figure 8: Screenshot of the notebook about the OpenIFS dataset: `load_nextGEMS_data` function.

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D3.3

4.3.4. ICON: Global climate projection setup (ICON-XPP)

Apart from the high-resolution setups commonly used for ICON simulations in the framework of ongoing flagship projects aimed at preparation for exascale, the ICON ESM is also still used for more common simulation setups aimed at long climate scales as required for global intercomparison activities like CMIP which provide the basis for the Assessment Reports (ARs) of the IPCC. These simulations cover much longer timescales than those in Sec. 4.3.2. due to significantly less use of compute and storage resources. Hence, we here provide a subset of data of the current ICON-XPP configuration (ICON-eXtendedPrediction and Projection) - a setup used for current state-of-the-art climate-scale simulations with horizontal grid spacings of about 80km (ICON grid R2B5) to be used for the German contribution to CMIP7 [4].

The data we provide here are 2D fields of a global, coupled simulation covering the time period from 1300 to 2300, at monthly output frequency.

<i>parameter</i>	<i>long name</i>
pres_msl	mean sea level pressure
pres_sfc	surface pressure
t_s	weighted temperature of ground surface
clct	total cloud cover
tot_prec_rate	total precipitation rate
tqv	total column integrated water vapour
tqv_dia	total column integrated water vapour (diagnostic)
tqc_dia	total column integrated cloud water (diagnostic)
tqi_dia	total column integrated cloud ice (diagnostic)
umfl_s	u-momentum flux at the surface
vmfl_s	v-momentum flux at the surface
sp_10m	wind speed in 10m
t_2m	temperature in 2m
sob_t	shortwave net flux at TOA
sod_t	downward shortwave flux at TOA
sou_t	shortwave upward flux at TOA
thb_t	thermal net flux at TOA
sob_s	shortwave net flux at surface
sou_s	shortwave upward flux at surface
thb_s	longwave net flux at surface
shfl_s	surface sensible heat flux
lhfl_s	surface latent heat flux
snow_con_rate	convective snow rate (convection scheme output for next time step)
snow_gsp_rate	gridscale snow rate
ice_gsp_rate	gridscale ice rate
qifl_s	surface cloud ice deposition flux due to diffusion
qhfl_s	surface moisture flux
t_seasfc	sea surface temperature
fr_land(ncells)	Fraction land
fr_seaice	fraction of sea ice
condhf_ice	conductive heat flux at sea-ice bottom

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D3.3

melpot_ice	melt potential at sea-ice top
t_ice	sea/lake-ice temperature
h_ice	sea/lake-ice depth
albvisdif	UV visible albedo for diffuse radiation
albvisdir	UV visible albedo for direct radiation
albnirdif	Near IR albedo for diffuse radiation
albnirdir	Near IR albedo for direct radiation

Table 8: Variable specification for the supplied ICON-XPP setup; Spatial resolution: 80km, temporal output frequency: monthly; time period: 1000 years preindustrial control simulation; NetCDF Data on unstructured ICON grid in S3 bucket "ICON-XPP"

A summary of this particular simulation, slo1802, is provided online [1]. The ICON data are provided as uncompressed netCDF and are publicly available in the [ICON-XPP directory](#) [10] of the ESiWACE S3 bucket. The total size of the data is approximately 147 GB. The data are available under the BSD-3-Clause license <https://opensource.org/license/bsd-3-clause>.

Three-dimensional data are also available, but were not transferred to the S3 bucket due to technical constraints on the data provider side¹. The data are provided on the native ICON grid, i.e. unstructured as a vector. Regridding the ICON output data to a regular lat-lon grid is possible and common. However, we provide the data on the native grid, since the regridding of the data inherently leads to a loss of information content and would obscure the impact of lossy compression applied to the data.

The data can be downloaded via the following link:

<https://object-store.os-api.cci1.ecmwf.int/esiwacebucket/ICON-XPP/>

A Jupyter notebook that explains the entire dataset, including a helper function to load the desired data into an `xarray`, is available here:

- <https://github.com/climet-eu/compression-lab-notebooks/blob/v0.2/04-example-datasets/04-ICONXPP.ipynb> on GitHub
- <https://compression.lab.climet.eu/v0.2/04-example-datasets/04-ICONXPP.ipynb> in the Online Compression Laboratory (see section 4.4)
- [doi:10.5281/zenodo.14526226](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14526226) on Zenodo

The notebook is structured similarly to the one explained in Sec. 4.3.1., so we only provide one screenshot explaining the helper function to load the data.

¹ The data had to be provided via a laptop, since the `s3cmd` CLI tool necessary for the data transfer to the ECMWF S3 store is not available on the HPC cluster where the data reside (DKRZ's Levante system).

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D3.3

Using the `load_ICONXPP_data` Function

To load the NetCDF files, you can use the following function:

```
load_ICONXPP_data(year=None, month=None)
```

Parameters

- **year**: An integer specifying the year for which data should be loaded. Available years: 1300 to 2300.
- **month** (optional): An integer specifying the month for which data should be loaded.

The datasets start on February 1st for years ending in `00` or `05`. If you need data for January 1st of these years, be sure to specify the appropriate month to load the correct dataset.

```
[1]: # URL of S3 bucket
BASE_URL = "https://object-store.os-api.ccil.ecmwf.int/esiwacebucket"
```

First, the package `zarr` (modern dataset format that is specifically designed for chunked access) and its dependencies need to be imported for the remote access.

```
[2]: import aiohttp
import cftime
import dask
import fsspec
import zarr
```

[pyodide]: Loading Jinja2, MarkupSafe, aiohappyeyeballs, aiohttp, aiosignal, asciitree, async-timeout, attrs, cftime, click, cloudpickle, dask, fsspec, jinja2, markupsafe, numpy, requests, zarr

The `load_ICONXPP_data` function simplifies remote access to NetCDF datasets stored on the S3 bucket. It validates input parameters, constructs the correct URL for the requested data, and loads it efficiently as an xarray dataset using the corresponding `.ref` file.

```
[3]: import json

import numpy as np
import requests
import xarray as xr

def load_ICONXPP_data(year=None, month=None):
    if not isinstance(year, int) or year < 1300 or year > 2300:
        raise ValueError("Please specify a valid year as an integer between 1300 and 2300.")

    if year == 2300:
        if not month:
            print(f"Warning: Only data for January 1st are available for 2300.")
            if month and month != 1:
                raise ValueError(f"Only data for January 1st are available for 2300.")

    if month:
        if not isinstance(month, int) or month < 1 or month > 12:
            raise ValueError(f"Please specify a valid month as an integer between 1 and 12.")

    file_year = (year // 10) * 10
    if not year % 10 <= 4:
        file_year += 5

    if not month and year % 5 == 0:
        if year == 1300:
            print(f"Warning: Data for January 1st of 1300 are not available as is is the simulation starting time.")
        else:
            print(f"Warning: Data for January 1st of '{year}' are stored in the previous file. Please specify the month to load the correct data.")
    elif month == 1 and year % 5 == 0:
        if year == 1300:
            raise ValueError(f"Data for January 1st of 1300 are not available as this is the simulation starting time.")
        file_year -= 5
```

Figure 8: Screenshot of the notebook about the OpenIFS dataset: `load_ICONXPP_data` function.

4.4. Infrastructure of the Online Laboratory for Climate Science and Meteorology

JupyterLab is a web-based frontend where the user can write (Python) code, inspect data, and run Jupyter notebooks. It is widely used throughout the scientific community for writing computational experiments, visualising data, and writing self-documenting example notebooks. JupyterLab typically requires a server on which the user-written Python code executes. This could be the user's local machine where they have installed JupyterLab, or a larger multi-user JupyterHub server that is hosted e.g. by a university or a supercomputing centre. In both cases, starting a new session has a setup cost, whether it is the creation of a new local Python environment in which JupyterLab is installed, or the provision of a container on the supercomputer for which the hosting needs to be paid for.

Over the last few years, the JupyterLab community has been working on JupyterLite, a variant of JupyterLab that does not require a (dynamic) server (only static file hosting) and instead runs entirely inside the user's browser using WebAssembly [16]. In the past, trying out JupyterLab would spin up a container on the BinderHub service. As JupyterLite has matured, it has now become the default for allowing users to try out JupyterLab within seconds and start executing scientific Jupyter notebooks.

How can JupyterLite run arbitrary user-provided Python code in the user's web browser without any server? Pyodide is a Python distribution that runs in the web browser using WebAssembly [22]. Put briefly, Pyodide compiles CPython (the default Python distribution) to WebAssembly using the Emscripten project and adds several utilities to interact with JavaScript and browser APIs from within Python. Pyodide also provides `micropip`, a simplified version of `pip`, with which Python packages can be loaded into the Python environment. While pure Python packages (those that only contain Python code) can be loaded without any changes, compiled Python extension packages, which are typically written in C/C++ or Rust, have to be compiled for WebAssembly and hosted in a PiPy-like registry (since PyPi does not yet support hosting Python packages compiled for WebAssembly). Therefore, the Pyodide project also contains an extensive list of such extension packages, including e.g. `numpy`, `scipy`, `sklearn`, etc. which provide the foundations of scientific computing in Python. Altogether, they (mostly) allow the user to run their Python code inside Pyodide without requiring any changes. JupyterLite uses Pyodide to provide the in-webbrowser Python kernel that executes the user's Jupyter notebooks.

While the Pyodide community already added support for many scientific Python packages before the start of ESiWACE3, many essential packages from the weather and climate (and Earth science community more generally) were not yet supported. One part of the development of the Online Laboratory has been about identifying and porting these packages to support Pyodide, including e.g. `basemap`, `Cartopy` [23], `cf_grib`, `cf_units`, `earthkit`, `eccodes`, `healpy`, and `netCDF4` [24]. We maintain a fork of Pyodide that includes these additional packages [26, 27, 30]. Some of these packages have already been contributed back to the broader Pyodide community (e.g. `Cartopy` [23] and `netCDF4` [24]) while others are currently only supported in the Online Laboratory (but will also be contributed over time). All ports are open-source.

The Online Lab provides significant contributions to loading large datasets inside Pyodide and JupyterLite. By nature of running inside the browser, JupyterLite is memory-constrained, typically to 2 GB per notebook and 2-4 GB per browser tab. Importantly, this includes datasets that are copied into the virtual filesystem that Pyodide runs in. However, we want to allow scientists to open weather and climate

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D3.3

datasets that are GBs or TBs in size. For the usecase where the dataset is already stored on the user's computer, we have developed the `ipyfilelite` JupyterLite extension [25] which uses the browser's File API to mount a user-provided file as read-only into the virtual filesystem, providing near-native reading speeds without copying the data themselves. For large datasets that are hosted remotely, e.g. in S3 buckets (see section 4.3), we rely on dataset chunking and data streaming to only fetch the data that are currently required by the user. Zarr datasets are natively chunked and support a variety of data sources through the Python `fsspec` package which abstracts over anything that can provide filesystem-like functionality (including S3 buckets and websites). NetCDF and GRIB files can be loaded as if they were Zarr files by using the `kerchunk` and `gribscan` libraries (see above). While this ecosystem of packages already exists to support loading large remote datasets, they could previously not all be used since `fsspec` required the use of threads, which are not yet supported in Pyodide. The Online Laboratory thus applies a series of invisible-to-the-user patches to `fsspec` and several other packages so that user-written code "just works" as-is. As a result, users of the Online Laboratory can seamlessly open chunked datasets of any size using their existing code without needing to worry about the magic making it work in the background.

In summary, the Online Laboratory provides an easy-to-access Python environment that runs server-less inside the user's own web browser and comes with common packages from the climate and weather community pre-installed. While it builds on existing community work on Pyodide and JupyterLite and continues to contribute back to these projects, it also provides several novel solutions to allow scientists to quickly jump in and experiment with compression on large datasets with ease.

The Online Laboratory is developed on GitHub at <https://github.com/climet-eu/lab> and is published under the Mozilla Public License 2.0. Our fork of Pyodide, which includes additional Python package ports, is developed on GitHub at <https://github.com/climet-eu/pyodide> and is published under the Mozilla Public License 2.0.

4.5. Community outreach, and the Online Laboratory as a service

We have built the infrastructure for the online laboratory to support our outreach on data compression to the weather and climate community and make it as easy as possible to test data compression on real data in Jupyter notebooks. Even though this outreach phase only started after the 3rd general assembly on 12.-13. November 2024 [28], we already presented the online compression laboratory at the Finnish National Hydrological and Climate Modelling Seminar on 20th November 2024 [29]. During the second half of ESiWACE3, we are planning further outreach using the laboratory to collect the community requirements for lossy data compression.

Importantly, we have built the online laboratory to be useful to the broader community beyond hosting the online compression lab. At its core, the online lab is like a containerized JupyterLab deployment that runs without a backend server directly in the user's browser and comes with common weather and climate science packages pre-installed. Therefore, it is ideal for sharing small code samples and providing interactive documentation while allowing the end-user to jump into executing code as fast as possible.

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D3.3

We are providing the online laboratory as a service to the broader community. To ensure that it is a stable tool that others can build upon, releases of the laboratory are published following semantic versioning [21] and all old versions remain accessible, allowing users to pin their examples to a specific version of the lab. The lab supports the following primary versioned entry points:

- <https://lab.climet.eu> or <https://lab.climet.eu/latest> both direct at the latest stable release
- <https://lab.climet.eu/v0.1.0> (and similar) directs at the specific released version 0.1.0
- <https://lab.climet.eu/v0.1> (and similar) directs at the latest release for the minor version 0.1, e.g. patch 0.1.1. Patch versions do not include breaking changes and only fix bugs, so targeting a specific minor version ensures that code runs in a reproducible environment and that bug fixes to this version can be benefited from.
- <https://lab.climet.eu/main> directs at the latest unreleased development version

For each version of the lab, a pip-compatible `requirements.txt` file is produced that pins the versions of all pre-installed packages, allowing users to reproduce the same versions later in a local Python environment.

While the above entry points simply open up a fresh session of the online lab, the lab also has the following additional endpoints to preload existing notebooks (where `:version` stands for one of the above versioned paths, e.g. `latest`, `v0.1.0`, `v0.2`, or `main`):

- https://lab.climet.eu/:version/github/:org/:repo/:branch/* downloads the provided GitHub repo, where `*` is an optional repository-relative file path. If a file path is given, it is pre-opened once the repo has finished downloading. GitLab repositories are supported using https://lab.climet.eu/:version/gitlab/:org/:repo/:branch/*.
- https://lab.climet.eu/:version/gist/github/:org/:gist/* downloads the provided Gist and pre-opens the provided file name. As Gists are already built to share small snippets of code, this link allows easily sharing executable Jupyter notebooks
- https://lab.climet.eu/:version/raw/github/:org/:repo/:branch/* downloads the provided single file path from a GitHub repo and pre-opens it. Repositories containing examples can provide specific links that make each file executable without requiring downloading all other files.

We are confident in the usefulness of these convenience URLs as we are using them ourselves. For instance, links to the online compression lab, e.g. <https://compression.lab.climet.eu/v0.1> are expanded to <https://lab.climet.eu/v0.1.0/github/climet-eu/compression-lab-notebooks/v0.1.0/README.md>, i.e. the online compression lab also just downloads the compression notebooks from their GitHub repository and opens the README file on startup. If e.g. a project such as ECMWF's `earthkit-plots` wanted to make their documentation examples (e.g. <https://earthkit-plots.readthedocs.io/en/0.2.1/examples/gallery/grid-types/reduced-gg-point-cloud.html>) executable, they could easily transform documentation links into online lab links (e.g. <https://lab.climet.eu/v0.1/raw/github-tag/ecmwf/earthkit-plots/0.2.1/docs/examples/gallery/grid-types/reduced-gg-point-cloud.ipynb>).

We hope that our online laboratory for weather and climate sciences proves to be a useful service to the broader community.

5. References

- [1]: DKRZ. (n.d.). *List of timeaverages for slo1802*. Available from: https://swift.dkrz.de/v1/dkrz_34406075a1684be9b56a2669a90730f2/ICON-Seamless/pyicon-slo/gp-slo1802/gp_index.html [Accessed: 12th December 2024]
- [2]: Diffenderfer, J. D., Fox, A. L., Hittinger, J. A., Sanders, G. D., & Lindstrom, P. G. (2019). Error analysis of ZFP compression for Floating-Point data. *SIAM Journal on Scientific Computing*, 41(3), A1867–A1898. Available from: [doi:10.1137/18m1168832](https://doi.org/10.1137/18m1168832)
- [3] Durant, M. (2021). *References specification – kerchunk documentation*. Available from: <https://fsspec.github.io/kerchunk/spec.html> [Accessed: 12th December 2024]
- [4]: DWD. (n.d.). *CAP7 - German contribution to the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CAP7)*. Available from: <https://www.dwd.de/EN/research/projects/cap7/cap7.html> [Accessed: 12th December 2024]
- [5]: DYAMONDS. (2021). *nextGEMS pre-final – easy.gems documentation*. Available from: <https://easy.gems.dkrz.de/DYAMOND/NextGEMS/prefinal.html> [Accessed: 12th December 2024]
- [6]: ECMWF. (2019). *ECMWF's vision for Big Data, AI and cloud computing*. Available from: <https://climate.copernicus.eu/sites/default/files/2019-11/Martin%20Palkovic.pdf> [Accessed: 12th December 2024]
- [7] ECMWF. (n.d.). *Parameter database*. Available from: <https://codes.ecmwf.int/grib/param-db/> [Accessed: 12th December 2024]
- [8] ECMWF. (n.d.). *Uncompressed 64-bit floating-point atmospheric and wave model outputs*. (n.d.). Available from: [doi:10.21957/r6rk-7978](https://doi.org/10.21957/r6rk-7978)
- [9] ESIWACE3. (2024). *ESiWACE3 Compression Datasets* [Dataset]. Available from: <https://object-store.os-api.cci1.ecmwf.int/esiwacebucket> [Accessed: 12th December 2024]
- [10] ESIWACE3. (2024). *ESiWACE3 ICON-XPP Compression Dataset* [Dataset]. Available from: <https://object-store.os-api.cci1.ecmwf.int/esiwacebucket/ICON-XPP/> [Accessed: 12th December 2024]
- [11] ESIWACE3. (2024). *ESiWACE3 IFS hplp Compression Dataset* [Dataset]. Available from: <https://object-store.os-api.cci1.ecmwf.int/esiwacebucket/hplp> [Accessed: 12th December 2024]
- [12] ESIWACE3. (2024). *ESiWACE3 NextGEMS Compression Dataset* [Dataset]. Available from: https://object-store.os-api.cci1.ecmwf.int/esiwacebucket/EW3_ICON_nqc4008_90d_Compression_test.zarr/ [Accessed: 12th December 2024]
- [13] ESIWACE3. (2024). *ESiWACE3 OpenIFS Compression Dataset* [Dataset]. Available from: <https://object-store.os-api.cci1.ecmwf.int/esiwacebucket/OpenIFS/> [Accessed: 12th December 2024]
- [14]: Granger, B. E., & Perez, F. (2021). Jupyter: Thinking and storytelling with code and data. *Computing in Science & Engineering*, 23(2), 7–14. Available from: [doi:10.1109/mcse.2021.3059263](https://doi.org/10.1109/mcse.2021.3059263)

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D3.3

- [15]: Huang, L., & Hoefler, T. (2022). *Compressing multidimensional weather and climate data into neural networks*. Available from: [doi:10.48550/arXiv.2210.12538](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2210.12538)
- [16]: JupyterLite developers. (n.d.). *JupyterLite – JupyterLite 0.4.5 documentation*. Available from: <https://jupyterlite.readthedocs.io/en/stable/index.html> [Accessed: 12th December 2024]
- [17]: Klöwer, M., Razinger, M., Dominguez, J. J., Düben, P. D., & Palmer, T. N. (2021). Compressing atmospheric data into its real information content. *Nature Computational Science*, 1(11), 713–724. Available from: [doi:10.1038/s43588-021-00156-2](https://doi.org/10.1038/s43588-021-00156-2)
- [18]: Liang, X., Zhao, K., Di, S., Li, S., Underwood, R., Gok, A. M., Tian, J., Deng, J., Calhoun, J. C., Tao, D., Chen, Z., & Cappello, F. (2022). SZ3: A modular framework for composing Prediction-Based Error-Bounded lossy compressors. *IEEE Transactions on Big Data*, 9(2), 485–498. Available from: [doi:10.1109/tbdata.2022.3201176](https://doi.org/10.1109/tbdata.2022.3201176)
- [19]: Lindstrom, P. (2014). Fixed-Rate Compressed Floating-Point arrays. *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics*, 20(12), 2674–2683. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1109/tvcg.2014.2346458>
- [20]: MPI-M. (2024). *NGC4008 - InterannualVariability documentation*. Available from: <https://m300281.gitlab-pages.dkrz.de/interannualvariability/simulations/ngc4008.html> [Accessed: 12th December 2024]
- [21]: Preston-Werner, T. (n.d.). *Semantic Versioning 2.0.0*. Available from: <https://semver.org/> [Accessed: 12th December 2024]
- [22]: Pyodide developers. (n.d.). *Pyodide – version 0.26.4*. Available from: <https://pyodide.org/en/stable/> [Accessed: 12th December 2024]
- [23]: Tyree, J., Choi, G., & Chatham, H. (2023). *Add package `Cartopy`*. Available from: <https://github.com/pyodide/pyodide/pull/3909> [Accessed: 12th December 2024]
- [24]: Tyree, J., & Chatham, H. (2023) *Add `netcdf4` package*. Available from: <https://github.com/pyodide/pyodide/pull/3910> [Accessed: 12th December 2024]
- [25]: Tyree, J. (2024). *GitHub - juntyr/ipyfilite: Zero-copy file upload widget for Pyodide kernels running in JupyterLite*. Available from: <https://github.com/juntyr/ipyfilite> [Accessed: 12th December 2024]
- [26]: Tyree, J. (2024). *Apply patches*. Available from: <https://github.com/climet-eu/pyodide/commit/488b76a0563b0b121f4a18d181756c83fbaa9945> [Accessed: 12th December 2024]
- [27]: Tyree, J. (2024). *Comparing pyodide:main ...climet-eu:climet-lab-0.27.0*. Available from: <https://github.com/pyodide/pyodide/compare/main...climet-eu:pyodide:climet-lab-0.27.0> [Accessed: 12th December 2024]

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D3.3

- [28]: Tyree, J., Faghieh-Naini, S., Dueben, P., Peters-von Gehlen, K., & Järvinen, H. J. (2024). *An Online (Compression) Laboratory for Climate Science and Meteorology: Exploring Data Compression from the Comfort of your web browser*. ESiWACE3 3rd General Assembly, Hamburg. Available from: [doi:10.5281/zenodo.14204539](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14204539)
- [29]: Tyree, J., Faghieh-Naini, S., Dueben, P., Peters-von Gehlen, K., & Järvinen, H. J. (2024). *Online Laboratory for Data Compression in Climate Science and Meteorology: Exploring Data Compression from the Comfort of your web browser*. National Hydrological and Climate Modeling Seminar, Finnish Meteorological Institute. Available from: [doi:10.5281/zenodo.14191942](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14191942)
- [30]: Tyree, J., & Pyodide developers. (2024). *GitHub - climet-eu/pyodide [fork]: Pyodide is a Python distribution for the browser and Node.js based on WebAssembly*. Available from: <https://github.com/climet-eu/pyodide> [Accessed: 12th December 2024]
- [31] UNIData. (n.d.) *NETCDF*. Available from: <https://www.unidata.ucar.edu/software/netcdf/> [Accessed: 12th December 2024]
- [32] Wieners, K., Rackow, T., Aguridan, R., Becker, T., Beyer, S., Cheedela, S. K., Dreier, N., Engels, J. F., Esch, M., Frauen, C., Klocke, D., Kölling, T., Pedruzo-Bagazgoitia, X., Putrasahan, D., Schnur, R., Sidorenko, D., Stevens, B., & Zimmermann, J. (2024). *nextGEMS: Catalogs of full output of the production simulations for ICON and IFS*. *World Data Center for Climate (WDCC) at DKRZ*. Available from: [doi:10.35095/WDCC/nextGEMS_prod_addinfo1](https://doi.org/10.35095/WDCC/nextGEMS_prod_addinfo1)
- [33] WMO. (2003). *Guide to the WMO Table Driven Code Form Used for the Representation and Exchange of Regularly Spaced Data In Binary Form: FM 92 GRIB Edition 2*. Available from: https://wmoorm.sharepoint.com/:b:/s/wmocpdb/EU0IxVC2a0xEhX7dCvXlRkABylpeZRGtlzu7fbByfGe_w?e=CugW30 [Accessed: 12th December 2024]
- [34]: Zarr developers. (n.d.). *Codec API – numcodecs 0.13.1 documentation*. Available from: <https://numcodecs.readthedocs.io/en/v0.13.1/abc.html> [Accessed: 12th December 2024]
- [35] Zarr developers. (n.d.). *Zarr*. Available from: <https://zarr.dev/> [Accessed: 12th December 2024]
- [36]: Zhao, K., Di, S., Dmitriev, M., Tonellot, T. D., Chen, Z., & Cappello, F. (2021). *Optimizing Error-Bounded lossy compression for scientific data by dynamic Spline interpolation*. *2022 IEEE 38th International Conference on Data Engineering (ICDE)*, 1643–1654. Available from: [doi:10.1109/icde51399.2021.00145](https://doi.org/10.1109/icde51399.2021.00145)

6. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered

No significant changes to the plans have occurred and no significant difficulty was encountered. However, the provision of non-compressed EC-Earth data was not possible due to the complexity of the IFS model. The atmospheric component of EC-Earth3 is based on an old version of IFS, which outputs data exclusively in GRIB format. By default, IFS fields in the output files are truncated, meaning they are not in 64-bit precision. While it is theoretically possible to modify the IFS source code to generate non-compressed GRIB files, the complexity of implementing this feature is prohibitively high and out of the scope of T3.3.

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D3.3

Instead, we considered it more plausible to use OpenIFS 43r3 to generate non-compressed data. This approach is aligned with the development of the new EC-Earth4 model, which uses OpenIFS (instead of IFS) as its atmospheric component. OpenIFS offers a significant advantage as it utilizes XIOS to output data in NetCDF format. This makes it straightforward to generate non-compressed data and provides an additional benefit: the NetCDF format stores separate metadata about the contained variables and is thus more convenient for exploring and testing various compression techniques compared to GRIB. Further details on the dataset are provided in Sec. 4.3.2.

7. How this deliverable contributes to the EuroHPC strategy

The datasets made available online for testing of various different compression techniques display the breadth of currently used weather and climate models and setups. These models, e.g. IFS, OpenIFS, and ICON, can be run on several EuroHPC machines. These models are also considered the staple of future weather and climate modeling activities in Europe on the way to exascale. Hence, evaluating the compression of output data from these models increases the usability of EuroHPC resources for the weather- and climate modeling community - now and in the future.

8. Sustainability

The datasets made available online will form the basis of domain-specific data compression analyses in the framework of ESIWACE3, i.e. during a hackathon and general outreach activities throughout the project lifetime. The datasets were chosen to span the entire spectrum of simulation setups to be expected for (pre-)exascale HPC setups. Therefore, we expect these datasets to be used for compression tests also in communities beyond the project partners. Eventually, the compression tests performed with the datasets provided will inform the recommendations for domain-specific compression of weather and climate model simulation output - a critical deliverable at the end of ESIWACE3 (D3.4) for which we expect large-scale uptake in the community.

9. Community engagement, dissemination, and exploitation

9.1 Target audience

As indicated in the Grant Agreement, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU).
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This report is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience:

The deliverable and the Online Compression Laboratory will be published to the ESIWACE3 Zenodo group and linked on the ESIWACE3 homepage. We will organise community outreach, including a hackathon, to explore compression techniques in detail together with domain scientists over the next two years.

ESiWACE3 Deliverable D3.3

9.2 Record of dissemination/engagement activities linked to this deliverable

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Date and location of the event	Type of audience	Zenodo Link	Estimated number of persons reached
Presentation	National Hydrological and Climate Modeling Seminar	20.11.2024, Helsinki, Finland	Finnish scientists	https://zenodo.org/records/14191942	50

9.3 Publications in preparation OR submitted

In preparation OR submitted?	Title	All authors	Title of the periodical or the series	Is/Will <i>open access</i> be provided to this publication?

9.4 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable

The software developed in the scope of Task 3.2 is open source and the data are available under the licences specified above.